

Student Perception of Home Background and the Acquisition of English Language in Mbonge Municipality

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ABSTRACT

The present study was intended to find out students perception of home background and the acquisition of English Language in Mbonge Municipality. Specific objectives were to examine how financial status of parent influence English language, investigate how educational level of the parents influence language acquisition, to examine how parent marital status influence English language acquisition and to find out how parenting style affect language acquisition. A descriptive survey research design was used on a sample of sixty (60) students using the simple random sampling technique. A closed ended questionnaire was used for the collection of data. The respondents were required to strongly agree, agree, strongly disagree and disagree to identify student perception of home background and its influence on language acquisition. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistic particularly frequencies, averages and percentages. The findings showed that, financial status of the parents influence English language acquisition, educational level of parents' influences language acquisition, marital status of parents influences English language acquisition and parenting style affect language acquisition. It was therefore concluded that students' perception of home background influence English language positively in Mbonge municipality.

KEYWORDS: perception, home background, acquisition, student, English language

INTRODUCTION

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Home literacy environments influence language and reading development. The home literacy environment is considered as the home literacy materials and experiences, such as exposure of story book reading and verbal opportunity for interactions, Parental literacy teaching activities and parents literacy habits (peeters, Simone, Nelessen, Fabbri, vanduffel, Rizzolatti, 2009).

English Language which could be classified as the world's language has suffered many malapropism (i.e. wrong usage of the words), mistake in phonetics (wrong pronunciation) and in Syntax (ungrammatical construction).

In a country like Cameroon where English Language is one of the official languages and a language of instruction, users especially students and pupils (learners) ought to equip themselves with the grammar of the language. In recent years, there has been a rampant usage of poor English Language and performance in schools and among learners, in terms of conjugation and phonetic expression both written and spoken; which in turn influences their learning outcomes.

In Cameroon, there exist many other languages such as: the indigenous, Pidgin, English and French Languages, their influence cannot be undermined as a contributive factor to the influence of the learners' inability to acquire English Language in schools.

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Observational studies of parent – child conversation show that parents rarely reinforce correct grammar in a child's speech, but tend to focus on the truthfulness or accuracy of statements. Taking this fact into consideration the ability of many students to use English Language well, can be trace back from the non environment where learners come from; which is a fundamental place where the acquisition of a language can begin effectively. The home background influences learners of English Language at the most critical time of their lives. That is when their minds are most receptive. It provides the first impression which may last through the whole of learner's life. The learner often sees the parents, siblings and others in their immediate environment to be most significant and that they are capable of promoting or diminishing her in her academic performance. There, the indispensability of the poor speaking and writing of English Language in our schools becomes an unquestionable concept, thus any weaknesses on our learners' acquisition of English Language in our schools becomes questionable and demands attention to be treated accordingly. Since English Language plays an important role in schools, who then is directly responsible for its influence on students perception and its acquisition? Since the society as a whole has an undeniable influence on learners acquisition of English Language, it should be noted that society is basically made up of the home environment at its core, thus the home environment plays an enormous role in learners acquisition of English Language, which in this case will ultimately be the

parents, caregivers, siblings and peer group usage of English Language in the home background.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Language around the world is English, and many people choose to learn other languages at home which affects their communication in school. During my practicum tour in some schools around the South West Region of Cameroon, the researcher realized that so many pupils and students could not speak good English. So many students were afraid and ashamed to answer questions in class because of their language. Some found it difficult to remember, master and use it logically especially when there were conversing with peers and teachers who were speaking in an alarmingly fast pace. Wrong use of English brought confusion to class and even the meaning of the conversations were not clear. The variations in the different forms of English were difficult to understand. The different between using formal and informal or the difference between spoken and written language was a big problem. Because of this gap the researcher deemed it necessary to research in this area so as to reduce the socio-cognitive gap.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Krashen's Theory of Second Language Acquisition

According to Krashen (1987) in his theory of Second Language Acquisition, there are two independent systems of second language performance: 'the acquired system' and 'the learned system'. The acquired system 'or 'acquisition' is the product of a subconscious process very similar to the process children undergo when they acquire their first language. It requires meaningful interaction in the target language - natural communication - in which speakers are concentrated not in the form of their utterances, but in the communicative act.

The "learned system" or "learning" is the product of formal instruction and it comprises a conscious process which results in conscious knowledge 'about' the language, for example knowledge of grammar rules. According to Krashen (1987) 'learning' is less important than 'acquisition'.

The Monitor hypothesis explains the relationship between acquisition and learning and defines the influence of the latter on the former. The monitoring function is the practical result of the learned grammar. According to Krashen (1987), the acquisition system is the utterance initiator, while the learning system performs the role of the 'monitor' or the 'editor'. The 'monitor' acts in a planning, editing and correcting function when three specific conditions are met: that is, the second language learner has sufficient time at his/her disposal, he/she focuses on form or thinks about correctness, and he/she knows the rule.

It appears that the role of conscious learning is somewhat limited in second language performance. According to Krashen, the role of the monitor is or should be minor, being used only to correct deviations from "normal" speech and to give speech a more 'polished' appearance.

Krashen (1987) also suggests that there is individual variation among language learners with regard to 'monitor' use. He distinguishes those learners that use the 'monitor' all the time (over-users); those learners who have not learned or who prefer not to use their conscious knowledge (under-users); and those learners that use the 'monitor'

appropriately (optimal users). An evaluation of the person's psychological profile can help to determine to what group they belong. Usually extroverts are under-users, while introverts and perfectionists are over-users. Lack of self-confidence is frequently related to the over-use of the "monitor".

The Natural Order hypothesis is based on research findings (Dulay & Burt, 1974; Fathman, 1975; Makino, 1980 cited in Krashen, 1987) which suggested that the acquisition of grammatical structures follows a 'natural order' which is predictable. For a given language, some grammatical structures tend to be acquired early while others late. This order seemed to be independent of the learners' age, background, conditions of exposure, and although the agreement between individual acquirers was not always 100% in the studies, there were statistically significant similarities that reinforced the existence of a Natural Order of language acquisition. Krashen however points out that the implication of the natural order hypothesis is not that a language program syllabus should be based on the order found in the studies. In fact, he rejects grammatical sequencing when the goal is language acquisition.

The Input hypothesis is Krashen's attempt to explain how the learner acquires a second language - how second language acquisition takes place. The Input hypothesis is only concerned with 'acquisition', not 'learning'. According to this hypothesis, the learner improves and progresses along the 'natural order' when he/she receives second language 'input' that is one step beyond his/her current stage of linguistic competence. For example, if a learner is at a stage 'i', then acquisition takes place when he/she is exposed to 'Comprehensible Input' that belongs to level 'i + 1'. Since not all of the learners can be at the same level of linguistic competence at the same time, Krashen suggests that natural communicative input is the key to designing a syllabus, ensuring in this way that each learner will receive some 'i + 1' input that is appropriate for his/her current stage of linguistic competence.

Finally, the fifth hypothesis, the Affective Filter hypothesis, embodies Krashen's view that a number of 'affective variables' play a facilitative, but non-causal, role in second language acquisition. These variables include: motivation, self-confidence and anxiety. Krashen claims that learners with high motivation, self-confidence, a good self-image, and a low level of anxiety are better equipped for success in second language acquisition. Low motivation, low self-esteem, and debilitating anxiety can combine to 'raise' the affective filter and form a 'mental block' that prevents comprehensible input from being used for acquisition. In other words, when the filter is 'up' it impedes language acquisition. On the other hand, positive affect is necessary, but not sufficient on its own, for acquisition to take place.

Social interactionist theory

Social interactionist theory is an explanation of language development emphasizing the role of social interaction between the developing child and linguistically knowledgeable adults. It is based largely on the socio-cultural theories of Soviet psychologist, Lev Vygotsky.

Initial stages

Approach to language acquisition research has focused on three areas, namely the cognitive approach to language

acquisition or the developmental cognitive theory of Jean Piaget, the information processing approach or the information processing model of Brian MacWhinney and Elizabeth Bates (the competition model), and the social interactionist approach or social interaction model of Lev Vygotsky (socio-cultural theory). Although the initial research was essentially descriptive in an attempt to describe language development from the stand point of social development, more recently, researchers have been attempting to explain a few varieties of acquisition in which learner factors lead to differential acquisition by the process of socialization; called the theory of "social interactionist approach".

Parenting styles

According to (Dauber, Epstein, 1993) parenting style is a psychological construct representing standard strategies that parents use in their child rearing. The quality of parenting is far more essential than the quantity of time spent with the child. For instance, a parent can spend an entire afternoon with his or her child, yet the parent may be engaging in a different activity and not demonstrating enough interest towards the child. Parenting styles are the representation of how parents respond and demand to their children. Parenting practices are specific behaviours, while parenting styles represent broader patterns of parenting practices.

There are various theories and opinions on the best ways to rear children, as well as differing levels of time and effort that parents are willing to invest.

Marital status

According to Maccoby et al (1983), a person's marital status indicates whether the person is married or single. Questions about marital status appear on many polls and forms, including censuses. The question has historically also appeared in job applications and credit card applications and similar contexts, though the practice is increasingly regarded as anachronistic as an answer would normally not be relevant to the consideration of the merits of an application, and may in fact be considered unlawful discrimination in some countries. In the simplest sense, the only possible answers are "married" or "single". Some unmarried people object to describing themselves by a simplistic term "single", and often other options are given, such as "divorced", "widowed", widow or widower, "cohabiting", "civil union", "domestic partnership" and "unmarried partners". In some cases, knowing that people are divorced, widowed, or in a relationship is more useful than simply knowing that they are unmarried. The category of "married" would also cover the situation of the person being "separated". In many cases people who are in a committed co-habiting relationship may describe themselves as married, and some laws require them to do so.

Questions about civil status appear on questionnaires for quantitative research, such as census forms and market research instruments. In a person's medical history, civil status is considered to have both quantitative and qualitative significance. A government records the civil status of its citizens by means of a civil registration system. Historically, inquiries into marital status have also appeared on applications for employment, loans, and credit.

Language acquisition

Language acquisition is the process by which humans acquire the capacity to perceive and comprehend language, as well as to produce and use words and sentences to communicate. Language acquisition is one of the quintessential human traits, because non-humans do not communicate by using language.

Following Makino (1980), language acquisition usually refers to first-language acquisition, which studies infants' acquisition of their native language. This is distinguished from second-language acquisition, which deals with the acquisition (in both children and adults) of additional languages. The capacity to successfully use language requires one to acquire a range of tools including phonology, morphology, syntax, semantics, and an extensive vocabulary. Language can be vocalized as in speech, or manual as in sign.

Human language capacity is represented in the brain. Even though human language capacity is finite, one can say and understand an infinite number of sentences, which are based on a syntactic principle called recursion. Evidence suggests that every individual has three recursive mechanisms that allow sentences to go indeterminately. These three mechanisms are: relativization, complementation and coordination (Makino, 1980).

Furthermore, there are actually two main guiding principles in first-language acquisition, that is, speech perceptual ways precedes speech production and the gradually evolving system by which a child learns a language is built up one step at a time, beginning with the distinction between individuals.

Philosophers in ancient societies were interested in how humans acquired the ability to understand and produce language well before empirical methods for testing those theories were developed, but for the most part they seemed to regard language acquisition as a subset of man's ability to acquire knowledge and learn concepts.

Some early observation-based ideas about language acquisition were proposed by Plato, who felt that word-meaning mapping in some form was innate. Additionally, Sanskrit grammarians debated for over twelve centuries whether humans' ability to recognize the meaning of words was God-given (possibly innate) or passed down by previous generations and learned from already established conventions: a child learning the word for cow by listening to trusted speakers talking about cows.

In a more modern context, empiricists, like Thomas Hobbes and John Locke, argued that knowledge (and, for Locke, language) emerge ultimately from abstracted sense impressions. These arguments lean towards the "nurture" side of the argument: that language is acquired through sensory experience, which led to Rudolf Carnap's Aufbau, an attempt to learn all knowledge from sense datum, using the notion of "remembered as similar" to bind them into clusters, which would eventually map into language.

Proponents of behaviorism argued that language may be learned through a form of operant conditioning. In B. F. Skinner's Verbal Behaviour (1957), he suggested that the successful use of a sign, such as a word or lexical unit, given a certain stimulus, reinforces its "momentary" or contextual probability.

Arguments against Skinner's idea of language acquisition through operant conditioning include the fact that children often ignore language corrections from adults. Instead, children typically follow a pattern of using an irregular form of a word correctly, making errors later on, and eventually returning to the proper use of the word. For example, a child may correctly learn the word "gave" (past tense of "give"), and later on use the word "gived". Eventually, the child will typically go back to learning the correct word, "gave". The pattern is difficult to attribute to Skinner's idea of operant conditioning as the primary way that children acquire language. Chomsky argued that if language were solely acquired through behavioural conditioning, children would not likely learn the proper use of a word and suddenly use the word incorrectly.

Parental educational level

Parental educational level is an important predictor of children's educational and behavioural outcomes (Davis-Kean, 2005; Dearing, McCartney, & Taylor, 2002). The majority of research on the ways in which parental education shapes child outcomes has been conducted through cross-sectional correlational analyses or short-term longitudinal designs in which parents and children are tracked through the child's adolescent years. Our main goals in the current study were to examine long-term effects on children's educational and occupational success of their parents' educational level while controlling for other indices of family socioeconomic status and the children's own intelligence, and to examine possible mediators of the effects of parents' education on children's educational and occupational outcomes. Following theory and research on family process models (Conger et al., 2002; McLoyd, 1989), we expected that indices of family socioeconomic status, including parent education, would predict the quality of family interactions and child behaviour. Next, based on social-cognitive-ecological models (Guerra & Huesmann, 2004; Huesmann, 1998; Huesmann, Eron, & Yarmel, 1987), we expected parental education, the quality of family interactions, and child behaviour would shape, by late

adolescence, educational achievement and aspirations for future educational and occupational success. Finally, following Eccles' expectancy-value model (Eccles, 1993; Frome & Eccles, 1998), we predicted that late adolescent aspirations for future success would affect actual educational and occupational success in adulthood. We use data from the Columbia County Longitudinal Study, a 40-year developmental study initiated in 1960 with data collected most recently in 2000 (Eron, Walder, & Lefkowitz, 1971)

How therefore, should students' perception and their ability to acquire English Language be by basically relying on the responsibility of the home background? What role should the school play in the students' acquisition of English Language? Should there be a cooperation of home background with the school in bringing about a balance level of students acquisition of English Language? This study therefore seeks to find out the influence of the home background on students perception on the acquisition of English Language.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design chosen for this study was the survey research design. The reason for this selection was based on the fact that data was collected from a small sample which was representative and the findings of the study generalized to the entire population. In addition, the study sought information through the use of a questionnaire and analyzed data from sample of students in relation to the students perception of home background and the acquisition of English Language.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

Sample Size

The sample here is made up of students from three secondary schools (Government High school Banga-Bakundu, Government High school Bombe and Apostolic Secondary School Banga), and a total number of 60 students.

Table1: Sample Size

S/N	Names of schools	Population of students
1.	Government High School Banga-Bakundu	20
2.	Government High School Bombe	20
3.	Apostolic secondary school Banga	20
	Total	60

Sampling Technique

The sampling technique used for this study was the random sampling technique (probability sampling). It was used in order to make sure that each element of the population has an equal probability of being selected.

Furthermore, ballots of folded papers which had "yes" or "no" were given to form 2, 3 and 4 students of the three selected schools to pick randomly. Those who picked "yes" were considered as the sample. This technique was used in order to avoid bias. The students who picked "yes" were given questionnaire to fill.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Table2: Showing mother level of education

S/N	Mothers level of education	F	%
1.	No certificate	13	21.7
2.	First school living certificates	23	38.3
3.	Ordinary level	14	23.3
4.	Advance level	6	10
5.	Degree holders	4	6.7
	Total	60	100%

The above table illustrates the respondents' mothers' level of education. From respondents' information concerning their mother's level of education, 13 of them were without any certificates with the percentage of 21.7%, parents with first school were 23 making a percentage 38.3%, 14 mothers were with Ordinary level given a percentage of 23.3%, 6 students mothers were Advance level holders with a percentage of 10% and 4 students mother were wit Degree holders with the percentage of 6.7%.

Table3: Showing Fathers level of education

S/N	Parents occupation	F	%
1.	No certificates	14	23.3
2.	First school living certificates	7	11.7
3.	Ordinary level	12	20
4.	Advance level	15	25
5.	Degree	12	20
Total		60	100%

The above table illustrates the respondents' fathers' level of education. From respondents' information concerning their father's level of education, 14 of them were without any certificates with the percentage of 23.37%, parents with first school living certificates were 7 making a percentage 11.7%, 12 fathers were with Ordinary level given a percentage of 20%, 15 respondents' fathers were Advance level holders with a percentage of 25% and 12 student fathers were Degree holders with the percentage of 20%.

Research question one: Financial status and its influence on English language

Analysis of data based on research question one which was "Financial status and its influence on English language". Findings were obtained using the closed ended questions. Five questionnaire items were used to determine student's views.

Table4: Showing the Frequencies, averages and percentages of students' responses

S/N	Questionnaire items	Positive responses				Negative responses				Total %
		f of SA	%	f of A	%	f of SD	%	f of DA	%	
1	My parents are financially capable to buy my language text books	24	40	34	56.7	2	3.3	0	0	100%
2	My parents can't speak English because they did not go to school	29	48.3	25	41.7	2	3.3	4	6.7	100%
3	My parents regularly speak but the dialect to me	1	1.7	6	10	31	51.6	22	33.7	100%
4	My parents provide me with home language teacher	15	25	33	55	4	6.7	8	13.3	100%
5	I attend very expensive school	29	48.3	25	41.7	2	3.3	4	6.7	100%
	Average	19.6	32.6%	24.6	41 %	8.2	13.6%	7.6	12.6%	100%
	Global percentages	73.6%				26.3%				

The above table analyses of objective one is in relation to the responses of students in the items found in the questionnaires on financial status and its influence on English language. An average of 19.6 students with a percentage of 32.6% strongly agreed to the mention that parents' financial status influences student English language acquisition in Mbonge Municipality. An average of 24.6 students agreed to the fact that parents' financial status influences student English language acquisition with a percentage of 41%, an average of 8.2 students strongly disagreed to the fact that parents' financial status influences student English language acquisition giving a percentage of 13.6%, while an average of 7.6 students with a percentage 12.6% disagreed to these facts. From the findings, it shows that, parents' financial status influences student English language acquisition in Mbonge Municipality with the global percentage 73.6 affirming to this question.

Research question two: Educational level of parents and its influence on language acquisition

Analysis of data based on the second research question was on "Educational level of parents and its influence on language acquisition" five questionnaire items were used to examine this objective.

Table5: Showing educational level of parents and its influence on language acquisition.

S/N	Questionnaire items	Positive responses				Negative responses				Total %
		f of SA	%	f of A	%	f of SD	%	f of DA	%	
6	My parents often corrects my language	30	50	20	33.3	4	6.7	6	10	100%
7	My parents attended higher level of education	10	16.7	17	28.3	22	36.7	11	18.3	100%
8	My parents discuss with me in English	12	20	12	20	21	35	15	25	100%

9	Pidgin and dialect is our home language	14	23.4	18	30	11	18.3	17	28.3	100%
10	my parents are aware of important of extra classes on language	22	36.7	11	18.3	10	16.7	17	28.3	100%
	Average	17.6	29.3%	15.6	26%	13.6	22.7%	13.2	22%	100%
	Global percentages	55.3%				44.7%				

The above table illustrates that educational level of parents influences English language acquisition. As shown above, an average of 17.6 students strongly agreed to the fact that educational level of parents influence English language acquisition with a percentage of 29.3%. An average 15.6 students also agreed that the educational level of parents influence English language acquisition with a percentage of 26%, an average of 13.6 students strongly disagreed to the fact that the educational level of parents influence English language acquisition with a percentage of 22.7% and an average of 13.2 students disagreed to the fact marking a percentage of 22% that educational level of parents influence English language acquisition. With the findings, it is seen that the educational level of parents influence English language acquisition of students in Mbonge Municipality with a global percentage of 55.3% positive responses.

Research question three: Marital status of parents and influence on language acquisition

Analysis of the findings is based on the third objective which was “To determine how Marital status of parents influence English language acquisition”. Five questionnaire items were used to examine this objective.

Table6: Showing how Marital status of parents influence students English language acquisition

S/N	Questionnaire items	Positives responses				Negative responses				Total %
		f of SA	%	f of A	%	f of SD	%	f of DA	%	
11	I often hear my parents speaking English	30	50	10	16.6	16	26.7	4	6.7	100%
12	I rarely meet my mother or father speaking dialect and pidgin English	21	35	21	35	12	20	6	10	100%
13	Student from single parents rarely speak English	19	31.7	14	23.3	19	31.7	8	13.3	100%
14	Students living alone speak English well	31	51.7	20	33.3	5	8.3	4	6.7	100%
15	Students language depend on parent marital status	19	31.7	8	13.3	19	31.7	14	23.3	100%
	Average	24	40%	14.6	24.3%	14.2	23.7%	7.2	12%	100%
	Global percentages	64.3%				35.7				

Items examined were three; I often hear my parents speaking English, I rarely meet my mother or father speaking dialect and pidgin English, Student from single parents rarely speak English, Students living alone speak English well and Students language depend on parent marital status.

The table above illustrate that an average of 24 students strongly agreed that marital status of parents influence students English language acquisition with a percentage of 40%. An average of 14.6 students agreed to the facts with a percentage of 24.3%, an average of 14.2 students with a percentage of 23.7% strongly disagreed to the fact that marital status of parents influence students English language acquisition and an average of 7.2 students disagreed to the fact that marital status of parents influence students English language acquisition. From the findings, it shows that, marital status of parents influence students English language acquisition positively with global percentage of 64.3 positive responses.

Research question four: Parenting style and its influence on language acquisition

Analysis of data based on the fourth research question was on “Parenting style and its influence on language acquisition” five questionnaire items were used to examine this objective

Table7: Showing Parenting style and its influence on language acquisition

S/N	Questionnaire items	Positive responses				Negative responses				Total %
		f of SA	%	f of A	%	f of SD	%	f of DA	%	
16	My parents have no time to correct my language	30	50	20	33.3	4	6.7	6	10	100%
17	My parents never look at my book	10	16.7	17	28.3	22	36.7	11	18.3	100%
18	My parents never find out about my difficulties on language	14	23.4	18	30	11	18.3	17	28.3	100%
19	My parents don't punish me when I	12	20	12	20	21	35	15	25	100%

	Speak Pidgin English									
20	My parents allow me to speak any language of my choice	22	36.7	11	18.3	10	16.7	17	28.3	100%
	Average	17.6	29.3%	15.6	26%	13.6	22.7%	13.2	22%	100%
	Global percentages	53.3%				46.7%				

As shown above, an average of 17.6 students strongly agreed that parenting style influences students language acquisition with a percentage of 29.3%. Students with an average of 15.6 also agreed that parenting style influences students language acquisition with a percentage of 26%, an average of 13.6 students strongly disagreed to the fact with a percentage of 22.7% and an average of 13.2 students disagreed with a percentage score of 22%. With the findings, it is seen that Parenting style influences language acquisition of students with global percentage of 55.3% affirming.

Research question one

Discussion of findings by research question one, shows that the financial status of the parents influences English language acquisition of students with a global percentage of 73.6%. The *raison d'être* for this is as a result of parents being financially capable to buy their children language text books, provide students with home language teacher and students attending well to do schools. This confirms Yarmel (1987) that children from low-income families are at a higher risk of entering school with poor language skills compared to more privileged students.

Furthermore, poor children have more difficulty understanding abstract language and possess lower reading and writing skills, which increases the odds that the child will drop out of school in the future. They often struggle with phonological awareness skills: the ability to consciously manipulate a language's sound system. There are many factors that contribute to this trend. Birth to the age of three is a critical period for language development, as the brain is rapidly growing and developing. Parents who are less educated may not know the importance of consistently using language with their baby, which can cause a delay in early language skills (Yarmel, 1987).

Research question two

Discussion of findings based on the second research question was on how educational level of parents influence English language acquisition. Findings showed that the educational level of parents influence English language acquisition with a global percentage of 55.3%. This shows that some parents often correct their children's language, some discuss with their children in English language and some with pidgin English and dialects.

In line this, Fathman (1975) asserts that home language always influence students learning in school since communication deals with language. Teachers and students use spoken and written language to communicate with each other—to present tasks, engage in learning processes, present academic content, assess learning, display knowledge and skill, and build classroom life. In addition, much of what students learn is language. They learn to read and write (academic written language), and they learn the discourse of academic disciplines (sometimes called academic languages and literacies). Students from home where the same language is used in school have high chances of performing high since there is a mutual understanding between the teacher and the learner (Todd, 2006).

Research question three

Findings based on the third research question determined how Marital status of parents influence language acquisition. The findings from the students showed that marital status of parents influence language acquisition positively with a global percentage of 64.3%. This was seen as students often heard their parents speaking English, and some students hardly hear their parents speaking dialect and students' language depends on parents' marital status.

According to Guerra & Huesmann (2004) parents marital status have an influence on the child language. To parents who are living together (married) will help the children acquire good language skills since their presence facilitates learning. Bandura (1969) confirms this view by attesting that learning is through observation and as such children can observe the way their parents talk and then imitate it.

Research question four

Parenting style influences language acquisition of children. From findings, parenting style influenced language acquisition with a global percentage of 55.4%. This shows that most parents do not have time to correct their children's language; many parents do not find out the difficulties their children are facing with language and many parents do not punish their children when they speak pidgin English.

Buttressing this, Dauber et al., (1993) aligns that parenting style has a big impact on how children develop language, and there are important implications for their future success. Hughes (2014) equally supported that Children of neglectful parents often have trouble following rules, because there has been few rules and little adherence to rules in their upbringing. Children of neglectful parents can have behaviour problems due to lack of self-control. Communication skills may also not fully develop. Indulgent parenting is characterized by attentive parents, who provide a great deal of warmth and interaction, but few rules and constraints. An "anything goes" attitude is typical of indulgent parents, and parents seem more like friends than parents. This parenting style often leads to higher levels of creativity in children and higher level of language development but there is little self-control, few boundaries, and a sense of entitlement. This can create one-sided interpersonal relationships, where the adult child of the indulgent parent is more willing to take than give Sieghler (2010).

CONCLUSION

The home background should stand as an interactionist environment where both parents and children share values that promulgate the acquisition of language for better performance in school. Despite the poverty stricken nature of some homes, exposition to socialization agencies ought to be the second and formal environment where children should develop high self esteem that enhances conversation among their peers and challenge them to take the bull by the horn.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bandura, A. (1969). *Principles of Behavior Modification*. New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston.
- [2] Dauber, S., Epstein J. L. (1993). *Parents and attitudes and practices of involvement in inner-city elementary and middle schools*. In N. F Chavkin (Ed), *Families and schools in a pluralistic society* (PP 53-71). Albany, Ny: SUNY Press.
- [3] Davis-Kean PE. (2005): *The influence of parent education and family income on child achievement*. The indirect rate of parental expectations and psychology. 19: 294-304.
- [4] Dulay, H.C, & Burt, M.K. (1974) *Natural Sequence in child Second Language Acquisition learning*, 24, 37-53.
- [5] Eron LD, Walder LD, Leskowitz MM (1971.). *Learning of aggression in children*. Boston: Little Brown;
- [6] Fathman, A. (1975). *Language background, age and the order of acquisition of English Structures* In M.K. Burt and H. C. Dulay (Eds), *On TESOL 75: New directions in Second Language Learning, Teaching and Bilingual Education* (PP 33-34). Washington D.C TESOL.
- [7] Eccles, J.A. (1998). Parents' influence on children's achievement-related perception. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, Vol. 74, 2, 435-452.
- [8] Guerra, N. G Huesmann LR. A Cognitive ecological model of aggression. *International Review of social psychology* 2004: 17:177-203.
- [9] Huesmann LR. (1998). *The role of social information in processing and cognitive schema in acquisition and maintenance of habitual aggressive behavior*. In: Green R. G, Donnersfein F, editors. *Human aggression: Theories research and implication for social policy*. San Diego, CA: Academic press.
- [10] Huesmann, L. R, Eron, L. D., & Yarmel P.W. (1987). *Intellectual Functioning and Aggression*. *Journal of personality and social psychology* 232-240.
- [11] Hughes (2014): www.spruegoose.org. Retrieve 10 March 2011.
- [12] Krashen, Stephen D. (1987.). *Principles and Practice in Second Language Acquisition*. Prentice Hall International,
- [13] Maccoby, E. E., & Martin JA (1983). Socialization in the context of the family: Parent-child interaction. In P.H Mussen (ed) and E.M. Hetherington (vol.ed), *Handbook of child psychology: vol 4 socialization, personality and social development* (4th ed. pp 1-101). New York: Wiley.
- [14] Makino. T. (1980). *English Morpheme Acquisition Order of Japanese Secondary School Students*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation. University of Mexico, Albuquerque.
- [15] McCartneg, K., E., & Taylor, B. A (2002). *Is high quality child care an intervention for children living in poverty?* Poster presented at the biennial meeting of the Society for Research in child Development, Tampa, FL.
- [16] Mclod, V. C (1989). Socialization and Development in a changing Economy: The Effects of paternakl job and income loss on children *American psychologist*, 44(2), 293-302.
- [17] Peeter R., Simone L., Nelisern K., FabbriDestro M., Vanduffel W., Rizzolatti G., el al (2009). The representation of tools use in Human and Monkes: *Common and Uniquely Human Features*. *J. Neurosci*. 2911523-1153/JNEUROSCI 2040.
- [18] Sieghler F. (2010). *Growing up in careless Home*, May Fair, York publisher.
- [19] Skinner, B.F. (1957.). *Verbal behavior*. New York: Appleton-century-croft: